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FEATURES OF DIAGNOSTICS OF CHRONIC RHINOSINUSITIS IN PATIENTS WITH VARIOUS FORMS OF CEREBRAL PALSY

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ANNOTATION

In this study, we investigated the relationship between the movement activity of cilia of ciliated epithelial cells performing the mucociliary transport function of the nasal mucosa and the level of calcium in blood serum. A total of 158 children aged 3–16 years with chronic rhinosinusitis were examined, including 98 patients with chronic rhinosinusitis associated with cerebral palsy (main group) and 60 patients with chronic rhinosinusitis without cerebral palsy (control group). The levels of calcium and 25(OH)D₃ in blood serum, as well as the functional activity of the nasal mucosa, were assessed. The results demonstrated that patients in the main group had significantly reduced levels of 25(OH)D₃ and calcium in blood serum (1.8 ± 0.14 mmol/L), which contributed to impairment of the mucociliary transport function of the nasal mucosa (30.9 ± 3.65 min). Correlation analysis between serum calcium concentration and mucociliary transport time revealed a direct positive relationship (+), with a moderate correlation strength (+65).

Keywords: cerebral palsy, chronic rhinosinusitis, hypovitaminosis D, hypocalcemia, mucociliary transport.

Introduction. In recent decades, perspectives on cerebral palsy in children have significantly changed, which has increased interest in studying the specific clinical

manifestations of this condition during treatment and rehabilitation processes [Rogov A.V., 2016]. It is known that this multifactorial pathology requires the involvement not only of neurologists and orthopedists, but also specialists from many other pediatric disciplines [Ratsig Ye.Yu., Bogomilskiy M.R., Laberko Ye.L., 2012; Yulish Ye.I., 2008]. Cerebral palsy in childhood is often accompanied by dysfunction of multiple systems, including visual and auditory impairments, speech disorders, symptomatic epilepsy, autonomic disturbances, secondary orthopedic complications, and various associated pathological conditions [Ma W., Silberberg S.D., Priel Z., 2002]. Therefore, many therapeutic and rehabilitation measures in children with cerebral palsy remain insufficiently effective. Even routine preventive vaccination schedules are often limited or omitted in children born with cerebral palsy. Among patients with cerebral palsy up to 18 years of age, disability is considered one of the most widespread neurological disorders [Kaladze N.N., Ponomarenko Yu.N., Moshkova Ye.D., 2014; Rogov A.V., 2016]. This condition creates serious difficulties not only for affected individuals but also for society as a whole. Modern multidisciplinary and comprehensive approaches aimed at children, adolescents, and adults with cerebral palsy are therefore considered the basis of contemporary healthcare strategies. For this reason, all recent achievements of modern clinical medicine should be actively integrated into the daily practice of specialists involved in the management of patients suffering from this neurological pathology. According to Kaladze N.N. et al. (2014), among 54 examined children with acute respiratory viral infections, 31 (57%) and among patients with chronic ENT infections, 18 (58%) had cerebral palsy [Rogov A.V., 2016].

According to literature data, approximately 70% of patients undergoing treatment for cerebral palsy experience seizure syndrome. This often necessitates long-term administration of anticonvulsant medications. Prolonged use of anticonvulsants may lead to impaired calcium metabolism. Under normal conditions, serum calcium concentration ranges between 2.1–2.6 mmol/L, while values below 2.1 mmol/L are regarded as hypocalcemia. Causes of hypocalcemia include disorders associated with vitamin D metabolism, gastrointestinal diseases, and pathological conditions

related to calcium-sensitive receptors. Certain medications, including anticonvulsants and depakine, inhibit the enzyme GABA-transaminase during metabolism and block GABA biotransformation. As a result, sodium-potassium ATPase activity in cell membranes decreases, T-type calcium channels are partially blocked, and calcium entry into cells is reduced. Barbiturates (phenobarbital, benzonal), anticonvulsants, and benzodiazepines activate cytochrome P-450, thereby intensifying hepatic vitamin D metabolism. Impaired vitamin D absorption in the intestine reduces calcium absorption and leads to hypocalcemia. A decrease in blood calcium concentration contributes to the development of pathological changes in many tissues. One of the affected systems is the ciliated epithelium, where the activity of epithelial cilia decreases [Ma W., Silberberg S.D., Priel Z., 2002; Abdurakhmonov I., & Shernazarov F., 2023].

The nasal cavity and paranasal sinuses possess several important protective mechanisms, one of which is the transport function of the mucosal epithelium. The removal of mucus produced in the nasal cavity mainly depends on two factors: the movement of epithelial cilia and the fluidity of secretions. The nasal mucosa acts as the primary protective barrier preventing dust particles and pathogenic agents from penetrating the respiratory tract. Neutrophils, macrophages, immunoglobulins, and ciliated epithelial cells participate in this defense mechanism. Secretions are produced by goblet cells located in the nasal mucosa. Together with ciliated epithelial cells, these secretions form the mucociliary transport system. Due to the coordinated activity of epithelial cilia, dust particles, microorganisms, and allergens adhered to the mucus are continuously removed toward the nasopharynx. In the pathogenesis of inflammatory diseases of the nose and paranasal sinuses, disturbances in the quantitative and qualitative characteristics of mucus play an important role and directly influence mucociliary transport activity. Alterations in the composition of mucus create favorable conditions for the proliferation of pathogenic microorganisms and contribute to the development of inflammation in the paranasal sinuses [Joskova M., Mokry Yu., Franova S., 2020; Shamsiev D.F., 2022].

The formation of mucus and the mechanisms regulating its composition remain insufficiently studied. The mucociliary system of the respiratory tract represents an inseparable component of the mucus layer and serves as the first protective barrier against harmful environmental influences. The protective function of ciliated epithelium largely depends on the composition of mucus. Normal rheological properties of mucus ensure adhesion of inhaled particles and their subsequent transport toward the nasopharynx. Under physiological conditions, this process usually takes approximately 10–20 minutes. The composition of mucus and the functional characteristics of ciliated epithelium maintain a balanced relationship with continuously entering microorganisms, thereby preventing colonization. Under normal conditions, mucus is produced by goblet cells and glands located within the mucosal epithelium. The ratio of goblet cells to ciliated cells is approximately 1:10. Goblet cells are predominantly localized in the mucosa of the paranasal sinuses. The secretions produced by the mucosa of the nose and paranasal sinuses are generally uniform in appearance. The total volume of secretions produced by goblet cells normally ranges from 8–10 ml per day. The upper layer consists of a gel-like colloidal structure.

The parietal layer represents a gel-like structure in which the cilia are located. Due to its complex composition, mucus forms a semi-liquid gel consisting of high-molecular compounds, polymers, sulfur-containing disulfide bridges, hydrogen bonds, Van der Waals forces, and intermolecular interactions, creating a three-dimensional structure. Chemically, nasal secretions contain approximately 95% water; when the pH decreases to 7.4–7.5, the gel transforms into a sol state. Changes in pH affect the fluidity, adhesiveness, and elasticity of mucus. Functional activity of the nasal mucosa can therefore be evaluated using indicators of mucociliary transport [Shchedrina I.O., Orlova K.A., Koltunov I.E., 2018; Shamsiev D.F., Voxidov U.N., Karimov O.M., 2018]. Tests determining mucociliary clearance are considered among the most objective methods for assessing the functional state of the nasal and paranasal sinus mucosa. Numerous techniques have been proposed to evaluate the transport activity of ciliated epithelium. At present, the saccharin test is

regarded as one of the most informative and widely recommended methods for studying mucociliary transport of the nasal mucosa.

Materials and Methods. The study was conducted during 2019–2021 at the Samarkand Medical Institute, including the pediatric neurology department of the university clinic and advisory polyclinic. A total of 158 children aged 3–16 years were examined, including 98 patients in the main group and 60 patients in the comparison group. Additionally, a control group consisting of 30 practically healthy children without pathology of the nose and paranasal sinuses was included. Chronic rhinosinusitis in 98 children with cerebral palsy was diagnosed based on ENT examination findings, anamnesis, rhinoscopy, pharyngoscopy, and computed tomography results. All patients underwent biochemical blood analysis with determination of serum calcium and 25(OH)D3 levels, as well as evaluation of the functional indicators of the nasal mucosa.

To assess mucociliary transport function of the nasal mucosa, the standard saccharin test was used. A small saccharin particle approximately 1 mm in diameter was placed on the lower nasal turbinate, about 1 cm posterior to its anterior edge, and the time until the subject perceived a sweet taste was measured using a stopwatch. During testing, patients were instructed not to swallow, cough, sneeze, or accelerate nasal breathing; swallowing was allowed once per minute. If medication could not be administered intranasally before the procedure, testing was postponed. The normal range of saccharin transport time varies considerably. If sweetness is not perceived after the established period, the test is repeated once more to exclude reduced sensitivity to saccharin. In addition to these methods, endoscopic techniques using methylene blue staining were applied to confirm mucociliary dysfunction.

To determine the pH of nasal mucus, special indicator paper was used. The indicator strip was directly applied to mucus collected from the nasal cavity, and the resulting color change was compared with a standard reference scale. According to published data, nasal mucus under physiological conditions demonstrates a mildly alkaline environment with an average pH of 7.015 ± 0.007 . Alterations in hydrogen ion concentration may occur for various reasons and can significantly affect

physiological functions of the nasal mucosa, including the frequency and strength of ciliary beating, viability of ciliated epithelial cells, and lysozyme enzyme activity involved in mucosal defense.

The absorptive and secretory functions of the nasal mucosa reflect the condition of blood supply within the nasal cavity and the functional activity of mucosal glands. These processes are regulated through the autonomic nervous system. Numerous factors influencing autonomic regulation can affect the absorptive and secretory activity of the nasal mucosa. For example, increases or decreases in ambient air temperature may alter hydrogen ion concentration in nasal secretions.

In our study, the absorptive function of the nasal mucosa was assessed using the method proposed by B.M. Sagalovich. According to this technique, one drop of a 1% atropine solution was instilled into the middle nasal passage for 15 minutes, and the reaction time of pupil dilation was evaluated.

We also investigated the secretory function of the nasal mucosa. Nasal mucus is produced by goblet cells and by the lymphatic system located within the mucosal layer. Nasal mucus contributes to humidification and purification of inhaled air particles before they pass into deeper portions of the respiratory tract, while lysozyme activity provides antimicrobial protection. To evaluate the secretory function of the nasal mucosa, we applied the method described by U.X. Shigabutdinov. For this procedure, cotton balls weighing 25 mg were prepared and measured on a torsion balance. The cotton balls were inserted into the patient's nasal cavity and retained for 10 minutes; afterward, they were removed and weighed again to record the results. Evaluation of absorptive and secretory functions of the nasal mucosa was performed with a one-day interval between tests.

Table 1. Functional Indicators of the Nasal Mucosa in Examined Patients

Indicators	Main group (n=98)	Comparison group (n=60)	Control group (n=30)
Mucociliary clearance time (min)	30.9±3.65	25.14±3.20	11.16±2.24
Hydrogen ion concentration of nasal mucus (pH)	7.33±0.06	7.33±0.08	7.11±0.06
Absorptive function of mucosa (mydriasis time, min)	76.92±2.78	77.92±3.75	65.42±2.32
Secretory function of mucosa (mg)	47.62±3.49	48.27±3.56	37.1±1.87

p≤0.05 compared with the control group; [^]*p*≤0.05 between groups.

According to the obtained results, patients in the main group demonstrated an average mucociliary transport time of 30.90±3.65 minutes, while in the comparison group the value was 25.14±3.20 minutes, and in the control group 11.16±2.24 minutes (Table 1). In healthy children from the control group, the average time from administration of saccharin into the nasal cavity to the appearance of a sweet taste in the oral cavity was approximately 5 minutes 19 seconds.

During examination of patients with rhinosinusitis, the pH level of nasal mucus averaged 7.33±0.06 in the main group, 7.33±0.08 in the comparison group, and 7.11±0.06 in the control group. Evaluation of the absorptive function of the nasal mucosa, assessed by pupil dilation time, showed average values of 76.42±2.8 minutes in the main group, 77.88±3.97 minutes in the comparison group, and 65.20±2.20 minutes in the control group. The secretory function indicator of the nasal mucosa was 47.62±3.49 mg in the main group, 48.27±3.56 mg in the comparison group, and 37.10±1.87 mg in the control group. Compared with the

control group, all parameters demonstrated statistically significant differences ($p \leq 0.05$).

It should be emphasized that most patients with cerebral palsy continuously receive neurological medications, including anticonvulsants, sedatives, and diuretics. One of the characteristic side effects of these medications is hypovitaminosis D, which leads to decreased calcium levels in the body. Calcium, in turn, is one of the main factors ensuring proper movement of cilia in ciliated epithelium. Studies confirmed that a reduction in calcium concentration weakens ciliary activity.

For this reason, our study additionally evaluated serum calcium levels and their influence on the transport function of the nasal mucosa.

Table 2. Results of Biochemical Blood Analysis in Examined Patients

Biochemical parameters	Main group (n=98)	Comparison group (n=60)	Control group (n=30)
Serum calcium (mmol/L)	1.8±0.14	2.08±0.17	2.28±0.16
25(OH)D3 (ng/ml)	15.9±3.3	24.9±3.3	30.5±3.8

The obtained data demonstrated that patients in the main group had lower levels of 25(OH)D3 and calcium compared with the comparison group. Decreased serum calcium concentration (1.8±0.14 mmol/L) contributed to deterioration of mucociliary transport function of the nasal mucosa, reflected by prolonged transport time (30.9±3.65 min). Correlation analysis between serum calcium levels and mucociliary transport time showed a direct positive relationship with moderate strength (+65).

Conclusion. Most children with cerebral palsy receive anticonvulsant and sedative medications for prolonged periods. The enzyme-inducing effect of these drugs accelerates vitamin D metabolism and reduces its concentration in the body. As a result, intestinal calcium absorption decreases, leading to hypocalcemia. Reduction of serum calcium weakens the force and frequency of ciliary movement, thereby

slowing mucociliary transport. Consequently, the functional condition of the nasal mucosa deteriorates, contributing to prolonged inflammatory diseases of the nose and paranasal sinuses.

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